

Diagram of Conceptual Model Research Manager Vision

Experiment Definition

Experimental Design

Experimental Execution

Symbology

- Undefined Concept (cloud shape)
- Concept (rectangle)

CRUD

- C = Create
- R = Read
- U = Update
- D = Delete

Role

- RM = Research Manager
- EM = Experiment Manager
- SrEx = Senior Experimenter

Events

R R C

RM EM SrEx